

A NEW REVIEW OF COVID-19'S ORIGINS DEMONSTRATES URGENT NEED TO RAISE GLOBAL STANDARDS FOR HANDLING PANDEMIC-POTENTIAL PATHOGENS

A RESPONSE TO *A CRITICAL REVIEW OF COVID-19 ORIGINS:
"HIDDEN IN PLAIN SIGHT"*

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WRITTEN BY
CHRISTINE PARTHMORE

Scowcroft Institute
of International Affairs

THE BUSH SCHOOL

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A New Review of COVID-19's Origins Demonstrates Urgent Need to Raise Global Standards for Handling Pandemic-Potential Pathogens

Christine Parthemore

This summer, Dr. Robert Kadlec published *A Critical Review of COVID-19 Origins: "Hidden in Plain Sight"* through Texas A&M University.¹ This extensive compilation of public-facing information and analysis follows past efforts by the U.S. Senate Health, Education, Labor, and Pension Subcommittee on Oversight and Investigations and other initiatives to better understand the origins of this horrible pandemic.² This study is essential for many reasons. One such reason is that it is a wake-up call to promptly advance discussions on stronger and more globalized standards for handling pandemic-potential pathogens and the high-containment labs in which related research is conducted.

These are not new issues, yet they should be treated with far greater prioritization in the years ahead. *Hidden in Plain Sight* is a reminder that such concerns perplexed policymakers even before COVID-19 caused millions of casualties (with the numbers still rising). While these are the baseline issues of what research should be pursued regarding pandemic-potential pathogens and how to most safely conduct such work, there is more to consider. We must also now grapple with additional trends that are changing the landscape of what research is conducted, and where and how that work is done, in many positive ways though also raising risks. As the number of high-containment labs continues to rise around the world, artificial intelligence (AI) is ever more infused into the biological sciences in ways that are reshaping the conduct of research, raising both great risks and opportunities. Further, the growing global bioeconomy is significantly expanding how research and applications involving living organisms are pursued outside traditional biocontainment approaches. Put simply, these issues were already challenging and growing more so over the past few decades, and that challenge is now being supercharged.

The first section of this essay briefly describes this baseline of trends related to high-containment labs that are at the forefront of policymakers' minds. Yet these issues are also evolving in multiple, significant ways, making the landscape even more complex, as described in the second part of the essay. As this will show, preventing future accidents and outbreaks on the scale of COVID-19 (and potentially far worse) requires the pursuit of cooperative risk reduction across nations and among public and private sector actors. This work should commence with urgency and be designed for the emerging nature of the biosafety and biosecurity landscape that will characterize the decades to come.

¹ Robert P. Kadlec, *A Critical Review of COVID-19 Origins: "Hidden in Plain Sight"* (College Station, TX: Scowcroft Institute of International Affairs, 2025), <https://bush.tamu.edu/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/A-Critical-Review-of-COVID-19-Origins.pdf>.

² Roger Marshall, *Muddy Waters: The Origins of COVID-19 Report*, (Washington, DC: Office of Roger Marshall), <https://www.marshall.senate.gov/wp-content/uploads/MWG-EXECUTIVE-SUMMARY-4.17-Final-Version.pdf>.

The State of Play with High-Containment Labs

The expanding number of high-containment labs is now well recognized. As of 2023, the Global Biolabs project that tracks such trends counted 69 biosafety level 4 (BSL-4) labs around the world: “51 BSL4 labs in operation, three under construction, and 15 planned, all spread over 27 countries.”³ The COVID-19 pandemic both drove many nations’ interests in increasing high-containment lab capacity and raised attention to the ongoing gaps in international transparency and standards regarding these facilities.

This trend is fueling numerous issues. Most directly, it raises concerns about the safety of workers in these labs and potentially the surrounding communities. Many nations have strong biosafety regulations or laws, and the World Health Organization (WHO) provides guidance to all nations. There are also many fora for bilateral, regional, and international cooperation for practitioners to trade information and best practices for biosafety and biosecurity. Yet nations still vary in their approaches to safety, and training, monitoring, and implementation remain uneven. Furthermore, there is no universal approach to considering the potential geography of impact should an accident occur from specific types of experimentation (e.g., whether more rural versus urban laboratories may be more appropriate for the conduct of certain work, if such options exist). Accidents can happen anywhere, and while significant safety and risk-reduction efforts are employed, these enduring gaps and challenges are real.

Moreover, there is no mechanism for nations to agree on the appropriate biosafety level for the conduct of specific types of experiments that are the most risk-inducing. For example, in early 2025, leading experts Dr. W. Ian Lipkin and Dr. Ralph Baric wrote a *New York Times* op-ed drawing attention to certain research conducted in China on a type of coronavirus with high human mortality potential. As they wrote, “after establishing that the virus can probably infect human cells, the researchers performed experiments with the fully infectious virus. They did not conduct these experiments in a BSL-3 or BSL-4 laboratory but in a laboratory described as BSL-2 plus, a designation that is not standardized... and that we think is insufficient for work with potentially dangerous respiratory viruses.”⁴ As the authors further describe, the experiments complied with China’s relevant regulations and were approved by local biosafety officers. This example is not meant to focus negatively on China, but to draw attention to the types of concerns that too often arise from the lack of globalized standards on, or oversight of, appropriate lab safety levels for pathogen research that could have global consequences.

Additionally, mistrust across nations is compounded by the lack of global approaches to managing risks at these labs—and to right-sizing the safety levels of experiments to begin with. When any nation builds a new high-containment lab or expands on existing spaces, this naturally drives questions regarding the types of activities they intend to host. For many countries, this extends to questions of whether the intended uses are solely peaceful and

³ Filippa Lentzos et al., *Global Biolabs Report 2023*, (London: King’s College London, 2023), 5, https://static1.squarespace.com/static/62fa334a3a6fe8320f5dcf7e/t/6412d3120ee69a4f4efbec1f/1678955285754/KCL0680_BioLabs+Report_Digital.pdf.

⁴ W. Ian Lipkin and Ralph Baric, “Recent Virus Research Should Raise the Alarm,” *New York Times*, March 3, 2025, <https://www.nytimes.com/2025/03/03/opinion/risky-virus-research.html>.

defensive, and aligned to obligations under the Biological Weapons Convention (BWC) not to pursue offensive weaponization of the life sciences.

To be sure, there are legitimate reasons for nations to maintain or pursue high-containment laboratories. The 2001 anthrax attacks in the United States led to lab capacity, biosafety, and biosecurity changes for this nation and several others. Epidemics drove part of the global growth in these facilities, as nations grappled with detection, testing, and responses to numerous transnational outbreaks in the decades before COVID-19. Other drivers included many nations striving for assets to fuel their technological advancement and credibility, concerns about health security threats stemming from conflicts in neighboring nations, and, in just the past few years, the devastation that COVID-19 itself wrought in every nation.

As Kadlec describes, China's expansion of high-containment labs—and also that nation's efforts to improve its biosecurity regulations—stemmed from these trends:

“In early 2014, Xi Jinping noted the strategic importance of China's first state laboratory BSL-4 high-containment lab. Xi stated that ‘the construction of the [WIV's] P4 [BSL-4] laboratory [was] of vital importance to Chinese public health.’⁴¹³ While the Wuhan BSL-4 lab was the first constructed, at least three others have been built, are under construction or are planned (Harbin, Kunming and Guangzhou, respectively). In 2020, there were at least 112 BSL-3 (including animal BSL-3) labs at 62 sites, up from 12 labs at three sites in 2002, and more than 1,000 BSL-2 labs in China.⁴¹⁴ The rapid increase in high-containment labs was government mandated. It reflected lessons learned after the 2002 SARS outbreak as well as the priority the CCP placed in pursuing dominance in global life science research.”⁵

Outside of China, in some cases, the rising global number of high-containment labs also reflects positive risk reduction efforts conducted in the past, in particular building appropriate facilities to house activities that were being conducted under less secure conditions. For example, the combination of the 9/11 terrorist attacks in the United States and the Amerithrax attacks (in which anthrax was distributed through the U.S. mail system) drove greater attention to global bioterrorism threats. A clear area of vulnerability was that potentially dangerous pathogens were stored in disparate places and under vastly different security conditions—in some cases, even housed in buildings with no locks on storage cabinets or rudimentary site security. Indeed, most nations had no map of where many specific high-risk pathogen samples existed across their territory. In response, the United States and other nations invested in new, far more secure, laboratories and worked with partner nations to consolidate the most dangerous samples into these locations. In addition to nations increasing their infectious disease detection and response capacities to stave off future epidemics and pandemics, this type of pathogen sample consolidation is a legitimate purpose, even if it augments the number of high-containment labs globally. Notably, some of these same laboratories were later the target of Russian disinformation that falsely cast them as housing bioweapons work.⁶

⁵ Kadlec, *A Critical Review*, 44.

⁶ U.S. Department of State, “The Kremlin's Never-Ending Attempt to Spread Disinformation about Biological Weapons,” March 14, 2023, <https://2021-2025.state.gov/the-kremlins-never-ending-attempt-to-spread-disinformation-about-biological-weapons/>.

Despite the clear trend, no international entity was charged with monitoring where such labs existed or were being built, leaving a fundamental gap in our understanding of biological risks and how to address them. The aforementioned Global Biolabs mapping project by Dr. Filippa Lentzos of King's College London and Dr. Gregory Koblenz of George Mason University is seeking to fill this gap with publicly available information, with major reports published in 2021 and 2023. In addition to mapping the expansion of BSL-4 facilities, their work calls attention to both examples of positive biosafety and biosecurity efforts—and the continuing lack of a committed international baseline of setting, applying, and monitoring the implementation of such standards. *Hidden in Plain Sight* presents one real implication of the gap in international monitoring of high-containment labs and the work conducted in them: the need for the meticulous hand collection of details related to this landscape, source by source. The fact that such a monumental effort was required to understand just one nation over a relatively short, finite timespan is a strong signal of the need for transparency and cooperation.

Hidden in Plain Sight also brings to life a dynamic many experts have raised for years, but that is discussed less publicly than issues such as the high costs of building and maintaining high-containment labs. Gaining a holistic sense of any nation's risk landscape and how best to mitigate those risks requires mapping different types of facilities of different biosafety levels and the nature of work undertaken across them. BSL-4 labs are not the sole focus of strong safety needs, even if they claim the largest part of the spotlight; nor do they capture the full range of risks (e.g., socio-political and economic) should incidents occur. Risk reduction requires a sense of how diverse but often interrelated types of dry lab and wet lab work would be conducted, including different types of pathogen research and approaches to learning, and how earlier-stage work connects to any animal experimentation that is conducted. Kadlec's work brings this issue to life in his discussion of the lack of information regarding where Brigadier General Yusen Zhou of the Beijing Academy of Military Medical Sciences Institute of Microbiology and Epidemiology conducted animal challenge studies on the COVID-19 vaccines that were under development, the fact that the animals involved may have come from Beijing, and the landscape of various facilities in the Wuhan area:

"The requirement for animal BSL-3 facilities and BSL-3 labs that could test primates would limit the locations where such work could be safely performed. Whether any of these challenge studies were performed at the WIV's Wuchang campus BSL-3 labs or at the Wuhan University Institute of Animal Models ABSL-3 primate facility is a matter of conjecture. What is not conjecture is the risk posed by conducting such animal vaccine challenge studies. As described by PLA engineers who designed and built China's high containment labs and biosafety equipment, infected animal research, such as vaccine challenge studies, will fill biosafety facilities with high-dose hazardous aerosols of highly pathogenic biological agents."⁷

While there are signs that Chinese researchers took enhanced safety precautions in some instances, any researcher would have had to navigate whether to take such steps in an environment lacking global definitions and standards on handling such circumstances. As the Global Biolabs report states regarding enhanced BSL-3s, for example, "there is very limited national biosafety guidance, and no international guidance, on what constitutes BSL3+ and little to no

⁷ Kadlec, *A Critical Review*, 48.

research demonstrating that these enhancements provide an adequate level of additional safety for the riskier research conducted in these labs.”⁸

The value of this mapping of biocontainment labs, and a deeper public understanding of what it takes to operate them safely, transcends borders. All nations encounter these types of operational needs, issues that arise from the specific research being pursued, ups and downs, and implementation challenges. Importantly, many details that Dr. Kadlec describes stem from China’s efforts to navigate change as the nation recognized the need for significant pandemic preparedness—and as it pursued research for which the risks were not fully understood, which is a challenge being navigated by the United States and many other nations.

This informs our reality today. Not only does the world need to advance baseline standards to de-risk the current global environment, but this must happen quickly if the world is going to be adequately prepared to navigate multiple emerging changes and trends.

Biosafety in a Rapidly Changing World

Interrelated trends will rapidly reshape the second half of this decade and the world that follows: the power and functions of tools available for conducting biological research, the diversification of actors performing such work, and the landscapes in which they operate.

First, it is now widely acknowledged that machine learning and AI tools are advancing at breathtaking speeds, generally speaking, and in terms of specific biological applications. One marker of this was the 2024 Nobel Prize in Chemistry going to a combination of two Google DeepMind AI researchers who developed AlphaFold 2 (which was released just three years before this Nobel Prize was awarded) to predict the 3D structures of proteins from amino acids far more accurately than anything to date; and David Baker of the University of Washington, a longtime pioneer in protein structure who has designed completely new proteins and remains a leader in developing and applying AI-fueled tools for designing new biological molecules (biodesign).⁹

Aside from such biodesign tools and the acceleration in discovery to which they are contributing, much attention has gone to questions of how the large-language models (LLMs) being developed by frontier AI companies will contribute to experimentation, and to how the nature of research will continue to change as all of these facets of AI advancement link with things like robotics and autonomy.

Notably, these sorts of tools could gain greater use in influencing decisions surrounding biosafety levels, lab activities, and whether and how research should move from computational experimentation to physical, wet lab work. In some cases, such tools may allow digital experimentation to advance much further before researchers even see the need to move to physical experimentation. They may also help scientists and biosafety officials better

⁸ Filippa Lentzos et al., “Global Biolabs,” accessed August 29, 2025, <https://www.globalbiolabs.org/>.

⁹ Catherine Offord, “Protein Designer and Structure Solvers Win Chemistry Nobel,” *ScienceInsider*, October 9, 2024, <https://www.science.org/content/article/protein-designer-and-structure-solvers-win-chemistry-nobel>.

understand the risks of certain types of experiments and aid in informing choices to use higher biosafety level facilities or practices.

Second, these and other changes in the toolkits available to researchers link to the ongoing evolution in who is conducting research, the nature of their work, and where and how they are conducting it. For example, the AI and machine learning biodesign tools used for the protein structure work referenced above have been released as open models for researchers to work with in myriad ways that policymakers cannot fully predict. Such tools will continue to advance the democratization of biological research and development in countless beneficial ways. They are also advancing efforts to leverage conventional and synthetic biology across an expanding range of fields far beyond biotechnology and medicine, including in the development of new materials, bioremediation, creating specialized organisms for functions like carbon capture, countless applications for fighting plant pathogens and enhancing food security, and more.

These shifts will characterize the biosecurity landscape more and more throughout this decade and show how the field will likely shift in the coming years and decades. This changing landscape set the stage for the “Spirit of Asilomar and the Future of Biotechnology” conference held in early February 2025, which marked the 50th anniversary of the 1975 Asilomar Conference on Recombinant DNA, where scientists and others advanced many of the biocontainment and safety standards in use today.

One conference sub-group focused on bio-based applications designed for use outside of laboratories and considered how new regulations or safety levels might apply in such circumstances. As a summary paper from this discussion described, “this theme addressed the growing field of engineered biological solutions specifically designed for intentional release into open environments, marking a departure from biotechnologies in which confinement to traditional laboratory or industrial settings has been the norm.”¹⁰ As the authoring and supporting experts also concluded,

“The same biological agent, placed into two different environmental contexts, could lead to different behaviors of the agent and, consequently, different impacts on the environment. As such, frameworks for their evaluation and governance cannot consider BBCCs [biotechnologies beyond conventional containment] based on their intrinsic biological properties alone. This distinguishes them from frameworks for conventional, contained biotechnologies, which often categorize cases based on their intrinsic biological properties.”¹¹

Additionally, the Spirit of Asilomar conference included discussions about the need for redlines or other approaches for the international community to agree on, including on avoiding narrow types of research that could pose extraordinary dangers, (e.g., mirror life), and developing potential future norms and governance approaches to reducing risks surrounding the creation of fully synthetic cells, while supporting the potentially-extraordinary

¹⁰ John P. Marken, “1.1 Towards Frameworks for Evaluation and Governance of Biotechnologies Beyond Conventional Containment,” Rice University, 2025, 1, <https://repository.rice.edu/server/api/core/bitstreams/c4f09f6f-a0f5-4142-9276-c9f74da39ef2/content>.

¹¹ Ibid, 2.

benefits of this field.^{12,13,14,15} While this particular conference pulled together international experts in these fields and many others, that moment reflected a wide range of scientific advancements that have been underway for some time and are continuing worldwide.

As these trends and lines of inquiry all show, the pace of change in this field already makes clear that in biosecurity and biosafety policy, even as we must speed up efforts to create global standards for the types of biotech and biomedical research and deployment that the world has conducted in the past, we must also build security and safety into the newer, AI-shaped biological landscape that has begun to emerge.

Conclusion

As Hidden in Plain Sight reminds us, safety regarding high-containment labs should be a concerted global conversation, and it should be pursued with urgency. This will have to tie into ongoing policy questions of whether some very specific types of experiments should be avoided due to the potential risks outweighing possible benefits, how to manage experimentation and use of biotechnologies that are applied outside of laboratory settings, and how AI and machine learning are influencing all aspects of this landscape.

There are numerous ways such efforts could proceed, building on conversations and analyses that experts around the world have been conducting for years. Governments may take the lead in convening the dialogues needed to build an agenda or roadmap for pursuing international standards and mechanisms. If governments do not pursue such foundational work in the coming years, nongovernmental actors should step up to do so. Ultimately, progress will require a concert of public and private actors representing a wide range of global dynamics. Other steps below the level of global standards include regular lesson-trading and transparency meetings by heads of the BSL-3 and BSL-4 labs operating worldwide. Concepts could be advanced for an international review panel or similar mechanism to weigh in on whether and how the highest-risk research should proceed, in order to move toward some universalized standards and relieve nation-states of the burden of making such decisions independently.

Put simply, there are countless options for enhancing biosafety and biosecurity regarding these issues. As such, what is critical is that multiple actors begin to step up and chart the highest-impact paths forward—and then pursue such work rapidly—to put nations and the world on the best possible track for averting future pandemic-scale events.

¹² Katarzyna P. Adamala et al., “Confronting Risks of Mirror Life,” *Science* 386, no. 6728 (2024): 1351–1353, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.ads9158>.

¹³ Marken, “1.1 Biotechnologies Beyond Conventional Containment.”

¹⁴ David A. Relman, “2.2 The Importance of Redlines in the Life Sciences,” Rice University, 2025, <https://repository.rice.edu/items/de72d6d3-16b6-4094-b6db-8cee33bb1046>.

¹⁵ James A. Smith et al., “4.1 Safeguarding the Benefits of Synthetic Cell Engineering,” Rice University, 2025, <https://repository.rice.edu/items/68032baa-915f-4777-b613-9641824be028>.

About the Author

Christine Parthemore is CEO of the Council on Strategic Risks (CSR) and Director of CSR's Janne E. Nolan Center on Strategic Weapons. Previously, she served as a senior advisor to the U.S. Assistant Secretary of Defense for Nuclear, Chemical, and Biological Defense Programs. Christine has received multiple public service awards for her work in the U.S. government, testified before Congress, spoken at the United Nations, authored or coauthored dozens of written works, and lectured at universities in the United States, Vietnam, and China. She holds degrees from The Ohio State University and Georgetown University.

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